

1 **The primary molecular defect in Brca1/2 mutant humans is accelerated transformation resulting**
2 **from inappropriate activation of homeobox transcription factors.**

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7 Heterogeneity of tumor tissue due to the presence of stroma and tissue-specific gene expression are
8 major complicating factors in the analysis of complex genetic variants that predispose to cancer. The
9 mechanism of action by which humans with BRCA1 mutation are predisposed to cancer remains poorly
10 understood. To address this limitation we measured total transcription in mammary organoids derived from
11 healthy humans and humans with BRCA1 mutation. We integrated this data with study of total
12 transcription in 3D organoids derived from wild-type breast epithelial cells or breast epithelial cells
13 depleted of BRCA1 using RNA interference. We discovered inappropriate activation of homeobox
14 transcription factors as a central molecular consequence of BRCA1 mutation in humans, including the
15 SRY-box transcription factor SOX6. Homeobox activation was accompanied by significant up-regulation of
16 the estrogen receptor (*ESR1*) and a recently identified co-factor of the estrogen receptor that has functions
17 in transformation in the breast and resistance in humans with hormone receptor positive breast cancer,
18 *GREB1*. Autocrine production of growth factors including FGF7, together with ESR1/GREB1 and
19 homeobox expression likely primed BRCA1-deficient humans for transformation. The data clearly
20 demonstrate a mechanism of action for cancer predisposition in humans with BRCA1 mutations and
21 suggest a specific importance for homeobox transcription factors in transcriptional events leading to
22 transformation in humans.
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Results

We studied total transcription in BRCA1 deficiency: by BRCA1 mutation, or by loss of BRCA1 expression, in two different settings: in non-transformed epithelial cells of the breast (MCF10A) cultured in 3-dimensions, depleted of BRCA1 by RNA interference (siRNA), or in the context of mammary organoid culture from BRCA1 germline mutant humans (containing endogenous BRCA1 mutation). We used as a reference transcriptome BRCA1-sufficient breast cancer cells grown in 3D culture, or healthy, non-transformed, BRCA1-sufficient (wild-type) mammary organoid.

Figure 1: BRCA1 deficiency results in aberrant induction of ESR1 and GREB1.

1a. ESR1 and GREB1 activation in BRCA1-depleted mammary epithelial cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
215552_s_at	0.015126	-4.6	-2.37711	-3.73	ESR1	1763/54675	96.8
210562_at	0.007359	5.82	-1.69104	2.71	GREB1	984/	98.2

1b. ESR1 and GREB1 activation in BRCA1 mutant human mammary organoids.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2099	1.66E-01	0.371	-1.383735	-0.5137406	238.26	ESR1	4423/18797	76.5
9687	9.97E-05	0.35	-3.891422	-1.3635477	312.25	GREB1	181/	99.0

Figure 2: BRCA1 deficiency results in unscheduled activation of homeobox transcription factors which function like oncogenes.

1a. Homeobox activation in BRCA1-depleted mammary epithelial cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
228214_at	0.034097	-3.46	-3.21457	-9.24E-01	SOX6	3243/54675	94.1
1555352_at	0.003632	-7.29	-1.09037	-3.38	FOXP2	515/	99.1
203603_s_at	0.011669	-5.01	-2.12271	-1.31	ZEB2	1426/	97.4
221282_x_at	0.040992	-3.24	-3.41038	-1.34	RUNX2	3746/	93.1

1b. Homeobox activation in BRCA1 mutant human mammary organoids.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
55553	2.40E-05	0.34	-4.224076	-1.4371407	139.81	SOX6	126/18797	99.3
93986	2.04E-03	0.709	-3.084393	-2.1871024	25.18	FOXP2	427/	97.7
9839	3.20E-01	1.06	-0.995435	-1.0548868	205.54	ZEB2	7000/	62.8
860	5.82E-02	0.32	-1.894505	-0.6053851	198.43	RUNX2	2191/	88.3

Figure 3: The embryonic factor FGF7 is activated by BRCA1 deficiency.

3a. FGF7 expression in BRCA1-depleted mammary epithelial cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1555103_s_at	0.061601	-2.77	-3.84756	-9.25E-01	FGF7	5195/54675	90.5

3b. FGF7 expression in BRCA1 mutant human mammary organoids.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2252	2.32E-07	0.402	-5.171693	-2.0768062	101.99	FGF7	62/18797	99.7

Figure 4: A molecule known as trefoil factor 1, TFF1, that is a differentially expressed breast cancer gene is induced in BRCA1-deficient contexts.

4a. Trefoil induction in BRCA1-depleted mammary epithelial cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205009_at	0.057274	-2.85	-3.76912	-1.8	TFF1	4910/54675	91.0

4b. Trefoil induction in BRCA1 mutant human mammary organoids.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7031	2.42E-05	0.351	-4.222175	-1.4801886	161.69	TFF1	127/18797	99.3

Discussion

We demonstrate here unprecedented priming of transformation by BRCA1 deficiency. Transformation has not yet occurred as measured by sensitive ECT2 detection (data not shown) but accelerated transformation is a secure conclusion based on the human BRCA1/2-deficient phenotype. The major molecular defect in BRCA1 deficient cells in humans is inappropriate activation of homeobox oncogenes. This occurs in the context of ESR1 and GREB1 activation. We recently described GREB1 as a major actor in breast cancer resistance. TFF genes may have functions in subtype selection (differentiation of the transformed cell to a tumor of a specific, committed subtype). We are now investigating the role transcription factors in general and more specifically, homeobox transcription factors play in fate determination (subtype selection) in breast cancer.